

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D3.2: Comprehensive plan for capacity building activities and training pills delivery (II)

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

4H	Quadruple helix
CfP	Call for Proposal
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EIC	European Innovation Council
EnOLL	European Network of Living Labs
ESCO	European Standard Classification of Occupations
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupations
T	Task
WP	Work Package

SUMMARY

This Deliverable is the second step towards the development of the capacity building programme for col-labers – socio-digital entrepreneurs who will be trained to boost local ecosystems and social-business bi-directional innovation dynamics. Moreover, a plan for the delivery of training pills and motivating short videos, will be presented. In this context, the deliverable can be seen as an addition and improvement to the deliverable 3.1, prepared in April 2023, offering a deeper insight and a more detailed schedule for the coming processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation ecosystems in European regions

There are approximately two million social economy enterprises in Europe, representing 10% of all businesses in the EU. Achieving the triple transition “green, digital and social” demands a paramount effort for including, in a more decisive manner, social economy enterprises, social innovators and entrepreneurs in our EU innovation ecosystems.

INTEGER, a Horizon Europe project that kicked-off on 14th-15th 2023 of February in Barcelona (Spain), addresses the following questions:

- How can we actively integrate social innovation actors in European innovation ecosystems? Or better, how can we get social and business-driven innovators to work together?

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of **healthy living and wellbeing**, INTEGER will bring forward three innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive and integrative EU innovation ecosystems:

- The INTEGER 4 Helix Collaboratory model to implement the next generation of living labs, the ‘**Col-laboratories**’ (common open house of all kinds of innovators and entrepreneurs interested in producing new products and services that come from business or social oriented innovation).
- An EU Healthy Living Collaboratory, a true **network of networks’ community** with the capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects.
- A new professional profile, the ‘**Col-laber**’ or ‘**Col-laboratory manager**’ as a multiplying agent of change in these integrated innovation ecosystems.

Col-laborathons (quadruple helix hackathons following the INTEGER methodology) will be held in 3 EU Regions (Catalonia, Hamburg and Krakow) to foster social innovation Minimum Viable Products and Services to upscale it throughout Europe by applying and testing the INTEGER 4H comprehensive model.

By facilitating **business-driven** and **social-driven innovations**, INTEGER seeks to accelerate new win-win games, local mission-driven synergies, groundbreaking coordination of actions, governance, implementation, uptaking and exploitation dynamics.

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is the second deliverable in Task 3.1. This task focuses on the co-creation of digital arenas for capacity building among innovation actors in the three project partner regions with a twofold axis: a) Bringing attention to the benefits of social innovation projects to the society through capacity building, and b) Developing business support services for social entrepreneurs (templates, manuals and other support material).

In April 2023, the INTEGER project team submitted D3.1, the Comprehensive Plan for Capacity Building Activities and training pills delivery (I). The deliverable provided an overview of the expected outcomes of this task: 1) the Co-creation of digital arenas, 2) Capacity building programme for quadruple helix communities, 3) the new professional profile of the col-laber and 4) the delivery of training pills.

Following the planning of task 3.1, this deliverable 3.2 serves as a more detailed elaboration of the materials to be developed. After the introduction it is divided in the following sections:

- Chapter 2 contains an outline of the contents and planned procedures of the above-mentioned capacity building for strengthening the role of the col-lab, focusing on the definition of the col-lab profile and explaining the planning for different activities that will be performed in the INTEGER project.
- Chapter 3 deals with the development of the so-called training pills, which are short explanatory videos for micro-learning. The chapter gives an overview about the topics that should be covered in the pills and the development process.
- Chapter 4 describes the time plan.

To summarise, the purpose of the training pills and the capacity building activities is to implement a bi-directional user-centric approach to offer social innovation actors the suitable business and professional skills to pursue their visions, aims and solutions that respond to the identified societal needs. Hence, the developed materials should enhance the collaboration between other actors within and across regional innovation ecosystems. The capacity building, as well as the training pills, also focus on engaging the business-driven innovation actors (investors, business angels, philanthropists, etc.) to broaden their scope, thus they are better equipped to understand the need for social innovators to access other sources of funding.

1.3 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

The task is embedded in Work Package 3 (WP3) – Regional Innovation Ecosystems’ as Collaboratory Testbeds and includes the building of the col-laborations and is strongly related to the activities of WP5, WP2 and actions such as the study visits under WP3. Furthermore, WP3 is deeply rooted on the progress made under WP4, specially on the definition of the INTEGER model, to which the capacity building plan responds.

The communication channels developed in WP5 will be used for the dissemination of the training pills as well as for the approach of cooperating partners in capacity building. The website (<https://integer4h.theglocal.network/>) is required to make the training pills available on a permanent basis, fostering longer-term impact and sustainability.

In addition, the information from both WP2, WP3 and WP4 is of significant use to incorporate the developed information of the project into the training pills and capacity building.

2 Capacity building and defining the col-labour profile

2.1 Building capacity of col-labourers

The INTEGER capacity building of col-labourers focuses on the following outcomes:

- Enhancing innovation and entrepreneurship skills
- Building relationships, networks and partnerships
- Fostering a culture of openness and trust
- Accelerating the learning curve (long lasting learning)
- Accelerating social-digital innovation profile
- Developing policies and frameworks that support quadruple helix collaboration.

To sustain the future of the professional profile of the col-labourer, the ESCO Classification of Occupations database has been examined to find appropriate profiles. According to the ESCO classification of occupations, the profile of **Social Entrepreneur**, code 1120.6, best meets the under-definition profile of the col-labourer. The description, essential skills and knowledge of the col-labourer will be aligned with this profile of social entrepreneur and sustain for the future after the project ensures business continuity.

The INTEGER project's regional partners are asked to support the development of col-labourers portfolio with their skills, competencies and knowledge. After their joint approval, the task leader will focus on defining the learning goals and outcomes in September 2023.

2.2 Col-labourers and social entrepreneurs

Col-labourers in the INTEGER project are social innovators with digital skills who can network and boost collaborations within and across regional ecosystems, perform matchmaking activities and bring together social, business and technology-driven innovators. They are also able to set up sustainable innovation quadruple helix co-creation arenas where socio-digital and business-driven innovations could thrive. According to the proposal, this is how the col-labourer profile will look like.

Following ESCO: Social entrepreneurs create innovative products or service models to tackle social and environmental challenges, pursuing through their profits a social mission that benefits a wider community or the environment. They often use a more democratic decision-making system by involving their stakeholders closely and strive to achieve change at a systems level by influencing policies, market evolutions and even mentalities. Alternative labels are eco-entrepreneur, green entrepreneur, social business founder, social business venture founder and social enterprise founder. The novelty of the INTEGER col-labourer will be the long term pursuit of:

- solid quadruple helix collaborations,
- driven by identified needs in the communities and contexts, thus the col-labourer will be a socio-digital entrepreneur driven by a negotiated and shared vision on the prioritised needs or challenges of a given context;
- long-term sustainability model addressing the bi-directional understanding of complementary profiles and types of innovators.

The proposed profile and the existing ESCO profile show the following similarities:

Col-laber	ESCO Social entrepreneur
Be able to network and realise ecosystems, perform matchmaking activities and bring together business and technological innovators.	Use a more democratic decision-making system by involving their stakeholders closely and strive to achieve change at a systems level by influencing policies, market evolutions and even mentalities.
Be able to set up sustainable innovation quadruple helix co-creation arenas where socio-digital and business-driven innovations could thrive.	Create innovative products or service models to tackle social and environmental challenges, pursuing through their profits a social mission that benefits a wider community or the environment.

Table 1: Col-laber compared to social entrepreneur

2.3 Essential skills and competencies

ESCO further defines essential skills and competencies for the social entrepreneur that align with the profile of the col-laber:

Skills & competencies	Description
Advocate for others	Deliver arguments in favour of something, such as a cause, idea, or policy, to benefit another person.
Apply business acumen	Take appropriate actions in a business environment to maximise possible outcomes from each situation.
Assess environmental impact – aligned with the Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Framework	Monitor environmental impacts and carry out assessments to identify and reduce the organisation's environmental risks while taking costs into account.
Assume responsibility for the management of a business or social initiative	Adopt and assume the responsibility that entails running a business, prioritising the interest of its owners, societal expectation, and the welfare of employees.
Conduct public presentations	Speak in public and interact with those present. Prepare notices, plans, charts, and other information to support the presentation.
Control financial resources	Monitor and control budgets and financial resources providing capable stewardship in company management.
Create social alliances, bonding and long-lasting networks and dynamics	Build cross-sector long-term relationships with stakeholders (from public, private or non-profit sector) to achieve common goals and address common societal challenges through their joint capabilities.
Deliver a sales pitch	Prepare and deliver an understandably constructed sales talk for a product or a service, identifying and using persuasive argumentation.
Develop professional network	Reach out to and meet up with people in a professional context. Find common ground and use your contacts for mutual benefit. Keep track of the people in your personal professional network and stay up to date on their activities.

Exert a goal-oriented leadership role towards colleagues	Embrace a leadership role in the organisation and with colleagues as to provide coaching and direction to subordinates aiming at the achievement of specific objectives.
Manage budgets	Plan, monitor and report on the budget.
Manage financial risk	Predict and manage financial risks and identify procedures to avoid or minimise their impact.
Manage fundraising activities	Initiate fundraising activities managing the place, teams involved, causes and budgets.
Monitor social impact	Monitor the practices of organisations and companies with regard to ethics and their impact on the larger community.
Perform business analysis	Evaluate the condition of a business on its own and in relation to the competitive business domain, performing research, placing data in the context of the business needs and determining areas of opportunity. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aware and ready to scale up 2. Capable for acceleration
Perform project management	Manage and plan various resources, such as human resources, budget, deadline, results, and quality necessary for a specific project, and monitor the project's progress in order to achieve a specific goal within a set time and budget.
Prepare ad hoc monitoring and visual data to show return on investment (SROI)	Define and implement a monitoring system. Collect data. Prepare charts and graphs to present data in a visual manner.
Promote organisational communication	Promote and nurture the efficient spread of plans and business information throughout the organisation by strengthening the channels of communication at its disposal.

Table 2: Skills and competencies description

2.4 Essential knowledge

ESCO also defined the essential knowledge the social entrepreneur should possess or achieve:

Knowledge	Description
Crowdfunding	The process of collecting money via the internet to fund a project or a business, using digital strategies to collect small amounts of money from a large group of contributors.
Design thinking	The process is used to identify creative solutions to problem-solving by putting the user at its core. The five stages approach-empathise, define, ideate, prototype and test-are meant to challenge assumptions and iterate solutions that are better suited to the needs of the user.
Impact investing	Investment strategy aimed at investing in organisations or initiatives with a social or environmental outlook, which in turn generates financial gains but also a positive impact in society.
Participatory decision-making	The process of giving ownership of decisions taken in an organisation to all its stakeholders in an open, transparent and inclusive manner.
Philanthropy	The private activities support social causes on a large scale, often by donating large sums of money. Wealthy individuals usually make these donations to a range of organisations to help them in their activities.

	Philanthropy aims at finding and tackling root causes of social problems rather than responding to consequences on the short term.
Results-based management	The management strategy is typically used by international governmental bodies (such as the United Nations) and civil society organisations to monitor and measure the performance and achievement of results of a project or policy. It focuses on results defined as outputs, outcomes and impact which help organisations to achieve strategic goals.
Social alliances	The creation of partnerships between different actors (businesses, non-profit organisations or public sector organisations) through which they share resources and knowledge for a common cause: typically to solve a social or environmental challenge.
Social entrepreneurship	The process of creating, managing and scaling up a venture in order to address social challenges.
Social innovation	Innovative models, products or services which meet a social need and consequently create new collaborations in the social field.

Table 3: Knowledge description

2.5 Col-laber training curriculum

During the lifetime of the INTEGER project, in total at least 60 individuals will receive training as col-labers. Three individuals from each of the three regions will be trained more intensively. The individuals represent the social, technology and business innovation domains. They will meet for one training day in Krakow in November, followed by a sequence of three online training webinars (the digital arenas).

Other individuals will follow appropriate online training courses and INTEGER training pills.

1. Physical training in one of the regions

In November 2023, nine members from Barcelona, Hamburg and Krakow will meet in person for one day. The location will be further defined. During that day they will receive the following training:

1. Welcome and purpose of the training
 - Meet colleagues from other regions
 - Exchange of international experiences
 - Receive insight information on the col-laber training, profile and requirements
 - Make the first step towards skills development and learning knowledge
2. Ice-breaking and learning to know each other
3. Introduction of the 3 project's regions Catalunya, Hamburg and Krakow
4. Assessment of skills and competencies and knowledge from the col-laber profile
5. Social innovation and successes – theory and practice
 - WHY
 - WHAT
 - HOW
6. Ecosystems creation and maintenance – theory and practice
 - WHY
 - WHAT
 - HOW
7. Evaluation of the day
8. Closing

2. Other capacity building activities

INTEGER further aims to train at least other 51 INTEGER quadruple helix enabling professionals, col-labers-to-be. INTEGER foresees the following concrete activities:

- **Digital arenas**

INTEGER will organise digital arenas. Compared to D3.1, considering the necessity of international exchanges between the regions, the content of the digital arenas has changed into:

- a. Online INTEGER international meetings comprising (among others) the following topics:
 - The power of social innovation
 - Quality of life of citizens
 - Healthy living
 - Digitalisation
 - Inclusive, sustainable and profitable social innovation (profit not only measured in economic terms but translated into terms of well-being, inclusion, etc.
 - (Social) Business development
- b. Templates and manuals for business development.

The digital arenas will be an online training of 2 hours each. The change compared to D3.1 entails less focus on regional or local meetings in regional or local languages.

- **Col-labor professional profile and curriculum**

The col-labor profile will be elaborated by defining the skills and competencies. The learning outcomes and goals will be defined and the col-labor curriculum will be based on the learning needs of col-labers. This will entail a co-creation process with the selected actors per region following the INTEGER spirit (bottom-up, quadruple helix, active participation, etc). The curriculum with existing courses and training pills will be finalised in December 2023.

- **Training pills**

Training pills are one of the most attractive formats in micro-learning. They are small content units linked to a question. They aim to impart knowledge quickly, effectively and attractively to the user. Short videos are usually used as the medium. The content and scheduling of the training pills are provided in the annex. The training pills will be finalised in February 2024. See the next chapter for more details.

2.6 Col-labor capacity building scheduling

The training programme will be developed by AFEdemy with the support of partners of three project regions (Catalunya, Hamburg and Cracow). The partners of the regions will also appoint trainees who will be trained to become a col-laborer in the corresponding region. The trainees will represent socially and business-driven innovators and the quadruple helices.

After finalising the col-laborer curriculum and the training pills, other regional representatives will follow several training activities to reach the performance indicator of 60 trained people.

Scheduling of the col-laber advanced capacity building:

1. In September 2023, the regions decide who will be appointed as trainees on behalf of the region. At least three people will be appointed per region, representing the social and business sector.
2. The trainees will have a physical meeting and training day in Krakow in November 2023, back-to-back to the Polish “col-laborathon”.
3. The trainees will also meet online in the digital arena in November and December 2023 and January 2024. These sessions will last 2 hours each. AFEdeMY and URV will prepare the arenas. External and internal speakers will contribute to the above-mentioned topics. Dedicated training pills will be included in the agenda.
4. Finally, the trainees will meet in a digital closing session to evaluate the capacity building training and receive their training certificate (February 2024).

Scheduling of the other capacity-building activities:

In February 2024, the curriculum for the col-laber will be finalised. The curriculum will be co-created with representatives from the regions. At the beginning of 2024, the curriculum will be offered to stakeholders from the participating regions and other interested people. Training pills will be included. After the training, representatives will receive proof of their participation officially provided by the coordinator iCAT. The KPI is to train 60 people in this way.

3 Training pills

3.1 Training pills in INTEGER

In the INTEGER project, training pills are to be created as short learning videos (with a maximum length around 5 minutes) that address specific target groups of the quadruple helix. Here, they are also meant to further support the capacity building activities, by giving knowledge incentives to possible col-labers. During the project, a total of 13 pills will be developed, bringing attention to the benefits of social innovation to the society. At least 5 of the videos will include an expert.

The following chapters will present a slightly different concept of the training pills compared to deliverable 3.1. The decisive new feature is the conception of a learning path, which is intended to encourage learners to explore more than just one of the developed learning contents. In addition to the slightly modified concept and an overview of all training pill topics. Moreover, a description for the publication on the website and a detailed plan for the development of the training pills, including an overview of selected experts, can be found.

3.2 The learning path

As an addition to Deliverable 3.1, all the pills in INTEGER are meant to be included in a learning path, which also brings a new thematic division of the videos (see section 3.3). The learning path leads the learner through three areas, that are described as in the following:

First, the **Integer pills** provide a basic understanding of the project and its goals. The **Col-labers pills** then explain the new position of the col-labers, before the actual **Training pills** will deal with specific content for the various quadruple helix areas. All three pill areas have a colour code that will be used to design the website section and the introduction slides of the respective pills.

3.3 Pills division

Regarding the thematic focus and the division of the training pills, the existing concept from Deliverable D3.1 “Comprehensive plan for capacity building and training pills delivery” has been modified. 13 video pills will be developed, which partly deal with new topics. The change is mainly based on a new division of the training pills into three categories: **Integer pills**, which introduce the Integer Project, **Col-labers pills**, which explain the profile and position of the col-labers, and **Training pills**, which deal with specific topics in the context of the newly

developed INTEGER Quadruple Helix Collaboratory model. Below there is an overview of the titles and categorisations of all video pills. Each pill will have a duration of about 3-5 minutes.

1. *INTEGER pills*

The INTEGER pills include a presentation of the INTEGER project (to get a clear understanding of the goals of INTEGER) with instructions on how to use the digital community platform, thelocal.network, which is the main digital channel to build a long-term bonding community in line with the aims of the Coordination and Support Action (CSA).

- **INTEGER pill 1: The Integer Project**
 - What is INTEGER
 - Aims of the project
 - Expected results
 - Where to find them (website integercollab.eu and teasing the INTEGER digital community)
 - **Expert:** Toni Caro

- **INTEGER pill 2: How to connect to the INTEGER digital community (via thelocal.network)**
 - What is thelocal.network and its aims
 - How to register to thelocal.network and use its functions
 - Connecting to the INTEGER digital community (teasing how to boost your projects)

2. *Col-laber pills*

Col-laber pills deal with the position and role of the col-laber as a crucial person to bring together the different actors of the quadruple helix. Below you will find an overview of the videos to be developed:

- **Col-laber pill 1: The Col-laber and its role as facilitator**
 - Finalised and published on the website and YouTube:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jNjWECfn_G8
 - **Expert:** Theda Minthe

- **Col-laber pill 2: How to do offline and online facilitation as a col-laber**
 - Finalised and published on the website and YouTube:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FL3gl0t9JaQ>

- **Col-laber pill 3: Which knowledge and skills can be helpful for a col-laber**
 - Based on the Col-laber curriculum and ESCO qualification (chapter 2).

- **Col-laber pill 4: How to set-up an initiative in social innovation through co-creation**
 - Choosing an innovation topic (based on identified gaps in your region).
 - Initiating a project (within thelocal.network) [PARTICIPATE].
 - Identifying and connecting to relevant partners from the quadruple helix (in your region) [CONNECT].

- **Col-laber pill 5: How to keep your INTEGER digital community engaged over time and boost your initiative**
 - Publishing content and articles [PARTICIPATE].
 - Get together in Channels and Conversations.
 - Disseminating also to the outside world.

3. Training pills

Training pills will deal with specific topics regarding the quadruple helix areas. Experts from each of the pilot regions will be heard and will illustrate how social innovation can support the different quadruple helix actors. In addition, interesting topics will be covered to stimulate interest in the INTEGER project. In the following you can find an overview of the planned Training pills:

- **Training pill 1: What is social innovation and why is it important**
 - Defining social innovation.
 - Explaining why social innovation is needed.
 - **Expert:** Blanca Herrero (TBC)
- **Training pill 2: How can the public sector foster social and business driven win-win games to enrich public policies for the benefit of society**
 - Highlighting the advantages that social innovation brings to public authorities.
 - **Expert:** Public authorities from the 3 regions (30 seconds each)
- **Training pill 3: How can academia benefit from social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing**
 - Highlighting the advantages that social innovation can bring to the academia.
 - **Expert:** Academia from the 3 regions (30 seconds each)
- **Training pill 4: How can businesses benefit from social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing**
 - Highlighting the advantages that social innovation can bring to businesses.
 - **Expert:** Proposed: Phillips Hub, BarcelonaActiva and KTP from Poland (30 seconds each).
- **Training pill 5: How to apply for public funding**
 - Why public funding is crucial for the sustainability of social innovations responding to societal needs and challenges?
 - Which funding instruments are available from public funding?
 - How to apply for public funding?
 - **Expert:** (1 per region and 1 at EU level)
- **Training pill 6: How to do social innovation and let others know**
 - Plan and do social innovation.
 - Disseminate the results of social innovation (refer also to the INTEGER digital community platform).
 - **Expert:** Carina Dantas

3.4 Technical guidelines

To ensure uniformity between the different training pills, there are fixed visual principles to use in the videos. Hence, all training pills will be created according to the same format. Below there is a list of the (audio-)visual principles that will be taken into account:

Including an introduction slide: Every training pill will include in introduction slide with the same design. According to the division in *Integer pills*, *Col-laber pills* and *Training pills* there will be specific colour code for the slide (see on the right the example of the introduction slide of Col-laber pill 1):

Using pictograms: For the graphical representation of information within training pills, pictograms will be used. These are intended to convey the content in a more lively visual way (see example on the right):

Including a reference slide: To make the videos end uniformly, there is a reference slide that will be used in all training pills (see example on the right).

Adding a professional voice-over and subtitles: Finally, the text of each training pill is spoken in by a professional voice-over to make the content of the video as understandable as possible. Furthermore, subtitles can be added to the videos using YouTube.

To get an idea of the visual implementation of the pills, you can already find the finalised *Col-laber Pill 1* and *Col-laber Pill 2* on YouTube and the Integer website:

Website: <https://integercollab.eu/video-pills/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@INTEGER-Collab/featured> and

<https://www.youtube.com/@INTEGER-Collab/videos>

3.5 Publication

The links to all the training and learning opportunities will be published on the platform and the website. Concretely under the following sections.

- INTEGER platform (theglocal.network) -> Facilitator's corner project group
<https://integer4h.theglocal.network/ideas/facilitators-corner>
- The INTEGER YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@INTEGER-Collab/videos>
- Integercollab.eu -> RESOURCES -> VIDEO PILLS
<https://integercollab.eu/video-pills/> RESOURCES

The publication of all finalised video pills is due in **February 2023**. An exact schedule can be found in the following section.

3.6 Delivery process

AFEdemy will always start dynamising the process for each pill by sending the script to the coordinator. For creating the scripts, AFEdemy will use a template (see example script in the Annex). After validation, there will always be a “call for action” to the partners who must support on the production of an expert video on the respective pill with the basis and guidance provided by AFEdemy. In this call for action, partners will get invited to do a second validation of the script and give inputs on the planned visuals. Afterwards, they will create an expert video until the provision deadline.

Once the script has been validated by the partners, AFEdemy will work on the graphic background. Once the expert video has been delivered, AFEdemy will work on the edition of the video pill. After the pill is finalised, it will be uploaded on the above-mentioned websites. The training pills will be shared on social media. For a detailed time plan, check the following delivery schedule in 3.7.

3.7 Delivery schedule

This schedule contains who is the target group, who will take care of the expert video provision and who will revise and publish all video pills. Moreover, it includes an overview of the time plan, including responsibilities, for all the video pills to be created (**INTEGER pills**, **Col-laber pills**, **Training pills**).

INTEGER pills								
Title	Target group	Script generation	Script validated by coordinator	Call for action date	Script validated by partner	Expert video provision	Post WEB + Social	Publication deadline
1: The Integer Project	General public	AFEdemy 21.07.23	i2Cat 27.07.2023	AFEdemy - 28.07.2023	SHINE	Toni Caro	i2Cat + SHINE	04.09.2023
2: How to connect to the INTEGER digital community (via the Glocal.Network)	General public	AFEdemy 21.07.23	i2Cat 27.07.2023	AFEdemy - 28.07.2023	SHINE	NONE	i2Cat + SHINE	04.09.2023

Col-laber pills								
Title	Target group	Script generation	Script validated by coordinator	Call for action date	Script validated by partner	Expert video provision	Post WEB + Social	Publication deadline
1: The Col-laber and its role as facilitator	Potential Col-labers	AFEdemy				Theda Minthe	i2Cat + SHINE	24.05.2023 (DONE)
2: How to do offline and online facilitation as a Col-laber	Potential Col-labers	AFEdemy				NONE	i2Cat + SHINE	24.05.2023 (DONE)

3: Which knowledge and skills can be helpful for a Col-laber	Potential Col-labers	AFEdemy 06.11.2023	i2Cat 09.11.2023	AFEdemy 10.11.2023		NONE	i2Cat + SHINE	Latest 29.12.2023
4: How to set-up an initiative in social innovation through co-creation	Potential Col-labers	AFEdemy 13.11.2023	i2Cat 16.11.2023	AFEdemy 17.11.2023		NONE	i2Cat + SHINE	Latest 29.12.2023
5: How to keep your INTEGRER digital community engaged over time and boost your initiative	Potential Col-labers	AFEdemy 20.11.2023	i2Cat 23.11.2023	AFEdemy 24.11.2023		NONE	i2Cat + SHINE	Latest 29.12.2023

Training pills								
Title	Target group	Script generation	Script validated by coordinator	Call for action date	Script validated by partner	Expert video provision	Post WEB + Social	Publication deadline
1: What is social innovation and why is it important	General public	AFEdemy 25.09.2023	i2Cat 28.09.2023	AFEdemy 29.09.2023	SHINE	(Blanca Herrero TBC)	i2Cat + SHINE	06.10.2023
2: How can the public sector foster social and business driven win-win games to enrich public policies for the benefit of society	Public authorities	AFEdemy 27.07.2023	i2Cat 28.07.2023	AFEdemy - 31.07.2023	HAM i2Cat KTP	1 Helix actor from each of the three regions HAM + I2Cat + UJ	i2Cat + SHINE	18.09.2023

3: How can academia benefit from social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing	Academia	AFEdemy 18.09.2023	i2Cat 21.09.2023	AFEdemy 22.09.2023	UJ HAM	UJ + UKE + URV	i2Cat + SHINE	20.10.2023
4: How can businesses benefit from social innovation for healthy living and wellbeing	Business	AFEdemy 23.10.2023	i2Cat 26.10.2023	AFEdemy 27.10.2023	URV KTP HAM	(Phillips Innovation hub TBC) / KTP / (Barcelona active TBC)	i2Cat + SHINE	24.11.2023
5: How to apply for public funding	General public	AFEdemy 04.12.2023	i2Cat 07.12.2023	AFEdemy 08.12.2023	HAM i2Cat	Hamburg Förderbank or 1 EU funding actor	i2Cat + SHINE	19.01.2024
6: How to do social innovation and let others know	General public	AFEdemy 05.02.2024	i2Cat 08.02.2024	AFEdemy 09.02.2024	SHINE	Carina Dantas	i2Cat + SHINE	23.02.2024

4. Conclusion and time plan

After the deliverable 3.1, the presented deliverable 3.2 gives a more detailed overview of the planning and concept for the capacity building, the curriculum and delivery of the training pills. The following timetable describes the next steps to be taken after the delivery of this report:

September 2023	Digital arena activities Finalise skills and competences for the Col-laber Regions decide about the three persons appointed as Col-laber
October 2023	Define learning outcomes and goals for the Col-laber
November 2023	Digital arena activities Training day in one of the regions
December 2023	Digital arena activities
January 2023	Digital arena activities
February 2024	Final meeting of the Col-laber training Sharing the Col-laber curriculum Training pills: Upload all Training pills to the INTEGER website Finalisation of the Col-laber curriculum

5. References

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6. Annex

Example Script – Training pills

Title:	Script for video pill: INTEGER PILL 1: The INTEGER Project
Date:	21.07.2023
Version number:	V1
Project name:	INTEGER

General information

- Expected duration when speaking at medium speed: 3-4 min.
- **LEGEND: [Green: Graphical video directions]**

SCRIPT

[Background: Logo Integer / Starting slide]

The following presentation video on the Integer project is the first of a total of 13 video pills that provide insights into the aims, and expected outcomes of the Horizon Europe project. You can access all of the pills through integercollab.eu when clicking on the tab “resources” and selecting the option “video pills”.

-Short break-

[Background: three pictograms for 3 Helix actors]

The INTEGER project wants to develop a new concept for approaching innovation ecosystems.

Since the Covid crisis, the European health systems are in a state of transition. During the pandemic, deficits were exposed in the health and wellbeing of the society. As a result of this situation, a range of social innovations have emerged, initiated by various social actors. These innovations have contributed positively, bringing benefits from social actors to the society.

In this context, the INTEGER project seeks to leverage the transition in the European health systems by better integrating social innovations into existing frameworks.

INTEGER is the abbreviation for “Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions”

The project should promote the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive, and integrative European innovation ecosystems.

To summarise it in the words of the project partner F6S:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H9BsxildXIs>

[Background: three pictograms for 3 Helix actors with arrows]

In this context, today's existing triple helix model develops innovations primarily through the interaction of academia, industry, and the government.

[Background: One pictogram will be added for social innovation]

Following the quadruple helix model, the INTEGER project aims at strengthening the role of an additional actor, social innovation through the civil society.

[Background: Circle appearing on social innovation emoticon with three integrated emoticons for entities, social entrepreneurs and society.]

“Social innovation” is the process of creation, realisation and dissemination of new social practices in different social spheres. In the quadruple helix, it is brought through civil society, including social organisations, social entrepreneurs or individuals. As social innovation entities already make up 10 per cent of the economy in Europe with approximately over 2 million Institutions, integrating these parties can be seen as a much-needed process.

In this way, actors could support each other and social innovation could be designed in a more sustainable way with bigger benefits for all parties. In the following, you can hear the university Rovira Virgili:

sec 25-33: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r97IIAvYVSM>

[Background: Collaboratory emoticon in the middle of the 4 helix emoticons]

To involve these social actors more and more in innovation and development processes, the INTEGER project creates a series of innovations, which are all based on the definition of the so-called Col-laboratories.

Col-laboratory is a neologism to express the next generation of quadruple helix living labs. Living labs describe an open innovation research field that aims to develop new products and services. Also, end users are involved in co-creation processes under real conditions.

[Background: Three emoticons with arrows -> Col-laboratories, the model and the Col-laber]

In this context, the following three innovative advantages are elaborated in INTEGER.

- The INTEGER Quadruple Helix Col-laboratory model, to implement this next generation of living labs, the mentioned ‘Col-laboratories’.
In this respect, INTEGER develops a concept of how social innovation actors can be better integrated into existing triple helix innovation systems.
- Moreover, a European Healthy Living Col-laboratory will be created, a network with capacity to work on social, tech and business-driven projects.

(show navigation through theglobal.network)

In this context, INTEGER has developed a social platform called “theglocal.network”, where actors of the four helixes can communicate and hack together! You can find out more about the platform and how to use it in the INTEGER Pill 2: How to use theglocal.network and the Col·laber Pill 2: How to do offline and online facilitation as a Col·laber.

- Lastly, also a new professional profile, the “Col·laber” or “Col·laboratory manager” will be created. The position is described as a multiplying agent of change within these integrated innovation ecosystems. Col·labers will be enablers or bridgers, which will be needed to train the helix actors to work together and to do the facilitation in the Col·laboratories. More information on the position of the Col·laber can be found in the Col·laber Pill 1 “The Col·laber and his role as a facilitator”.

[Background: EU map with the three regions highlighted.]

In INTEGER, these innovations are developed and implemented within three European pilot regional ecosystems: Barcelona (Spain), Hamburg (Germany) and Krakow (Poland). The aim is to identify differences within these regions and to strengthen a European innovation community.

[Background: A circle with emojis for the below-mentioned points is appearing on top of the EU map]

In this context, INTEGER addresses a number of objectives, aiming to improve the existing interplay of innovation ecosystems:

1. Boost win-win games between business and social-oriented innovations addressing common challenges.
2. Transform co-creation dynamics into disruptive and tangible new products, services or competencies.
3. Co-design jointly public innovation policies.
4. Develop capacity-building of the new generation of socio-digital entrepreneurs and ecosystems’ enablers, the Col·labers;

(Include video cut from theglocal.network)

Here also a dedicated section in the “glocal.network” has been developed, the so-called “facilitators corner”, where Collabers can get together through conversations and shared contents and find out more about their tasks as facilitators.

5. Generate funding and investment mechanisms for social innovation start-ups and SMEs to develop and scale up game-changing innovations.

[Background: Introduction slide expert]

In the following, the project coordinator Toñi Caro will give you an impression of how the project INTEGER can contribute to a transformation and why this is so important!

[Video: Toñi Caro]

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tu2UV-9N_6Y

[Background: Closing slide with a cutscene of integer website]

Have you become interested in INTEGER?

Find out more about the INTEGER project by visiting its website integercollab.eu. In addition, you can also access the digital community platform at theglocal.network. More information on how to use it can be found in the INTEGER pill 2: How to use theglocal.network?